

Ethics through the Curriculum of the Faculty of Engineering

Carola Hernández Hernández¹, Nicolás Sánchez-Díaz²

¹ Profesora Asociada, Unidad de Apoyo a la Docencia, Decanatura, Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de los Andes.

² Asistente Graduado de Investigación, Unidad de Apoyo a la Docencia, Decanatura, Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de los Andes.

Email: c-hernan@uniandes.edu.co, n.sanchezd2@uniandes.edu.co

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062516>

Abstract

Engineering education in the 21st century faces significant challenges due to changes related to sustainability, globalization, the use of information and communication technologies, and complex social problems that require reviewing the role of engineers in society. One is the analysis of engineering solutions' social, environmental, and cultural impact, which is a critical element for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, and the reflections on professional ethics derived from this.

Engineering faculties are responsible for identifying educational options to ensure that their students develop the skills expected of them. Ethical competence dynamically articulates knowledge, know-how, and being with the specific aspects that make up ethical action (Montoya & Santiago, 2024). However, a long tradition of understanding engineering ethics as an individual matter and following codes of professional obligations (Lee et al., 2019; Gwynne-Evans et al., 2021; Mitcham, 2009) implies a challenge to the broader view of the competition.

This document uses a case study to present the proposal of the Center for Applied Ethics of the Universidad de los Andes proposal around the teaching of ethics through the curriculum in the Faculty of Engineering, identifying the achievements and challenges this process has faced throughout its implementation. The document presents, in addition to a historical perspective of the role of ethics in engineering and its education, the development of the mainstreaming of ethics as the ideal of the work of ethical competence, recognizing the participation of teachers and the review of the micro-curriculum as a contribution to the process.

Keywords: Ethics across the curriculum; Engineering education; Ethical perspective; Teachers' development.

1 Towards a historical perspective of ethics in engineering

When conducting a historical review of the relationship between ethics and engineering, the causal effect between the role of engineering practice and its assumed ethical perspective in a given context can be evidenced. Mitcham (2009) provides a historical account of the vision of ethics in engineering in the United States, which can be organized into four stages.

In its first stage, which includes the period between 1600 and 1800, ethics within the engineering framework are characterized by obedience to social hierarchy. This respect is directly linked with the predominant military values of the time and social relationships established from hierarchical power.

This characterization of respect or subordination remained in force until the first decades of the 20th century, when the second stage of professional engineering development would occur. This second moment was characterized by the emergence of ethical codes from various engineering associations; the codes of the American Institute of Electrical Engineers (AIEE) appeared in 1912, and the ethical codes of the American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE) and the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) appeared in 1914.

In this historical period, loyalty was in the public interest, and the public good was directly related to fidelity to the company. The previously mentioned codes made explicit the guidelines for protecting the interests of the client and the employer. Social welfare was understood as the welfare of the company.

Simultaneously with the appearance of engineering associations, which comprises the third stage, the objective of technical perfection and efficiency appears at the center of the discussion of engineering work. In this way, questions are introduced around the unequivocal fulfillment of employers' commercial interests to give rise to their own standards of good and wrong from technical criteria that allow the generation of better products.

From this, the paradigm of technical development is assumed to be a path for human progress. However, this resulted in technical decisions becoming the primary purpose of engineering, creating final products that did not necessarily contribute to the generation of social welfare.

The scene of the end of World War II and the geopolitical contexts of the Cold War bring with them a new ideal of ethics in engineering, generating an alternative to the perspectives of loyalty and efficiency by focusing their analysis on the social effects of engineering interventions and the adjacent responsibility to the profession. This sets up the fourth stage, characterized mainly by recognizing the importance and social implications of the professional role of engineering. Following this, Figure 1 graphically summarizes the historical timeline described so far.

Timeline of the history of ethics in engineering

Figure 1. Engineering ethics timeline. Own elaboration based on Mitcham's (2009) text

In the 1970s, the IEEE published its code of ethics, analyzing the impact of engineering on people's lives. In other words, the code proposed that the ethical development of engineering works contemplated responsibility for public welfare. On the other hand, interactions between engineering and philosophy professors increased, with discussions that revolved around the need to understand the ethical formation of engineers beyond technical issues (Mitcham, 2009).

In 1980, the Engineers' Council for Professional Development (ECPD) reoriented its educational function towards certifying engineering programs in the United States. In this way, the Engineering and Technology Accreditation Board (now called ABET—Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology) sought to ensure compliance with the seven fundamental canons formulated by the Engineers' Council (Mitcham, 2009).

The United States government supported the publication of three books on ethical education in engineering in the 1980s. Thus, Albert Flores and Robert Baum, Mike Martin and Roland Shinzinger, and Stephen H. Unger managed to publish their works that addressed aspects such as reflection on case studies, historical references, the need for articulation and incidence of professional societies, social experimentation, the implications of engineering practice, among other elements.

Despite the efforts, the discussion of ethics in engineering was nothing more than a space for individual reflection on professional responsibility. With this condition, creating courses dedicated to the study of ethics in engineering was an alternative that did not appropriately, practically, and explicitly cover the ethical implications of engineering. Chance et al. (2021) conducted research in which they asked about decision-

making in civil engineering, and the term ethics did not appear as a factor to consider. However, they did refer to protecting the environment and improving people's quality of life.

At the beginning of the 21st century, ABET proposes 11 expected outcomes for individuals graduating from engineering programs. Criterion 3f establishes "an understanding of professional and ethical responsibility," and criterion 3c includes some other ethical considerations: "the ability to design a system, component or process to meet desired needs within realistic limitations such as economic, environmental, social, political, ethical, health and safety, manufacturability, and sustainability" (ABET, 2015). This explicitly called for the pedagogy of teaching ethics in engineering without the need to guide specific content and to materialize the commitment to ethical competence with a more humanistic vision of engineers beyond established codes (Beever & Brightman, 2014; Bucciarelli, 2008; Lee et al., 2019).

After implementing the first accreditation criteria in 2000, engineering faculties were encouraged to define evaluation and improvement objectives for their programs while giving them greater flexibility to achieve them. The results (Lattuca et al., 2006) showed that many programs managed to improve transversal professional skills without affecting the development of technical skills. A student-centered learning approach was adopted, using design projects, teamwork, case studies, improving feedback, and emphasizing skill development.

By the end of the 2010s, ABET decided to trim down the expected outcome criteria from 11 to 7 to train engineering professionals. Criterion 4 states that engineering professionals should have "the ability to recognize ethical and professional responsibilities in engineering practice by making informed judgments, which must consider the impact of engineering solutions in global, economic, environmental, and social contexts" (ABET, 2023). The actions proposed by ABET pose a challenge to the widespread student perspective that courses focused on ethics are of little importance compared to those that develop technical components. As the text unfolds, the contribution of the Center for Applied Ethics at Los Andes University (CEA) in driving this transformation within the Faculty of Engineering will be highlighted.

2 Ethics across the curriculum

From the Center for Applied Ethics at Los Andes University, an approach to Ethics across the curriculum is proposed, which, among other things, involves thinking about ethics throughout life, through the curriculum, and life through the University (Montoya & Santiago, 2020). This conception aims to understand the individual as an integral being for whom ethical reflection makes sense in various scenarios and is worth being taught explicitly. Throughout university life, the student is conceived in all their dimensions, beyond the skills associated with professional work, considering aspects that constitute the human condition.

The CEA's vision of ethics throughout the university revisits Dewey's idea that "we do not educate directly but through the environment" (Dewey, 1916, cited by Montoya and Santiago, 2020). This implies constituting appropriate contexts that allow the visibility of ethics in all university areas. Therefore, although the CEA focuses on teacher training, elements of an organizational nature and the university's social responsibility are addressed by the Vice-Chancellor of Research and Creation and the Vice-Chancellor for Development.

The work of the CEA is oriented towards a dynamic approach to the curriculum, proposed as the design of the students' educational experiences at the university (Montoya, 2013). Likewise, the university has opted for a competency-based curriculum that recognizes the complexity of educating individuals by adequately integrating knowledge, skills, and attitudes that allow them to act appropriately in various situations. Therefore, creating a curriculum that promotes ethical competence requires a link between ethical knowledge and disciplinary content with practical implications for students.

Understanding ethics through the curriculum in this way, the primary strategy is the design of Epsilon courses that contemplate that “professors of all disciplines and professions incorporate an objective of ethical training in their disciplinary course, which implies the design of a sequence of teaching, learning, and evaluation that accounts for their achievement” (Montoya & Santiago, 2020, p.193). This methodology exposes students to multiple educational experiences and the concepts of philosophical ethics through ethical deliberation tools that allow them a tangible approach to their contexts.

The great challenge this proposes is that engineering professors, as proposed by Bucciarelli (2008), stop forgetting ethics as part of their professional responsibility or express that they are not qualified to teach the subject, focusing their teaching work towards the world of objects free of values. Assuming a leading reflective role around the implications of engineering in real contexts allows the humanization of the engineer and engineering itself.

3 Ethical Education in the Faculty of Engineering

In 2023, the Faculty of Engineering at the Universidad de Los Andes is organized into seven departments and offers ten undergraduate programs, 19 master’s degrees, four specializations, and two doctoral programs. Its mission is to educate highly competent engineers in technical, ethical, and personal aspects, enabling them to lead social transformations and improve the quality of life by transferring knowledge, technological innovation, and solution design.

Figure 2 chronologically organizes how the discussion on ethics has advanced in the Faculty of Engineering at Los Andes University. It presents the most relevant events.

Figure 2. Ethics across the curriculum in the Faculty of Engineering of Los Andes University. Own elaboration

Throughout its history, the Faculty of Engineering has had a close relationship with the education provided in the United States (Universidad de Los Andes, n.d.). This allowed students of the Faculty to spend their first semesters in Bogotá and then travel to major universities in the United States to complete their studies. Likewise, this close link allowed the Faculty to stay updated on discussions about the quality of engineering education. The ABET accreditation attests to this.

As recorded in Figure 2, in 2002, the Faculty directed its curricular reform towards developing competencies and including pedagogies oriented towards learning by doing. These reforms took place in 2005. Simultaneously, in 2003, the Professional Ethics Code was adopted by enacting Law 842. This law obliges the faculties of Engineering to identify ways to make it known to their students and proposes, as happened in the United States, the need for an education that includes professional ethics.

After ten years without accreditation in Colombia, ABET resumed the process in the country. In 2008, the Faculty carried out the self-evaluation exercise under the 11 criteria proposed by ABET at the time. The eight programs of the Faculty were accredited. It is essential to highlight that the accredited programs reformed their content-based curriculum to a competency-based curriculum.

The CEA created the course Tools for Teaching Ethics to support the professors pedagogically. This contributed to a training scenario to reconsider the courses, strengthening their ethical component and, thus, the idea of the Epsilon courses. To date, 46 professors have been trained in ethics pedagogy in an active, student-centered, and contextualized form. This exercise allows professors to be part of the Epsilon community, where interested professors share their course design, the experiences they carry out, and the reflections that arise from these implementations, thus enriching the pedagogical reflection on the teaching of ethics.

By implementing these actions that empower professors regarding ethical aspects in their courses, students receive the correct message that facilitates their learning. From a curricular perspective, providing professors with these pedagogical tools facilitates the transformation of practices and the materialization of the logic of ethics through the curriculum (Lattuca et al., 2006).

Engineering teachers' involvement in rethinking the ethical component of their courses is related to two significant events for the faculty: Firstly, curricular reflection was carried out at the University between 2014 and 2019 (Langebaek et al., 2020). The duration was modified there, and a visible axis was established in Colombia for the Uniandes Basic Cycle (CBU). In addition to explicitly analyzing Colombian problems, a degree requirement was established, and all students must take an Epsilon-type course within their CBU courses.

Secondly, by 2017, the Faculty had developed a level of discussion and reflection that allowed it to face the ABET reaccreditation process, starting from the approach proposed by the curricular reform. At this point, the CEA's offer gained more value, and its contribution to the process was evident. It is fundamental to mention that this reform, far from seeking to unify the different departments, gave them the independence to strengthen their identity and simultaneously build the idea of the Faculty (Duque & Reyes, 2020).

The critical idea representing a structural innovation within the reform is to bet on project-oriented courses as interdisciplinary spaces. In developing these courses, students from various areas of engineering face real challenges in generating solution prototypes in the contexts of companies, organizations, and communities. For this, students must resort to many cross-competencies, among which ethical reflection gains importance through the students' analysis environment.

This project-oriented course approach allows engineering students to approach real situations in their profession's development and contemplate ethical considerations that would not otherwise be significant in their training process and lives. These scenarios address the need posed by the 21st century to expose students

to tasks beyond solving a given problem and present them with a real scenario in which problems do not arrive as an exercise to be solved in a book. However, it is the same interdisciplinary interaction that allows for the characterization of a situation as problematic, as well as finding within this deliberation the ethical implications of the intervention of each discipline (Figueiredo, 2021).

Aligned with this course perspective, the Vice-Chancellor of Research and Creation conceptualized the π (Pi) type courses. These training spaces start from the context of 'learning by doing' and seek to strengthen the skills associated with the research/creation of students (Universidad de Los Andes 2, n.d.). Within the teaching team that supports these courses, a doctoral student acts as a tutor, supporting the course's research and bringing aspects of research ethics to the discussion.

While Epsilon professors lead many project-based courses in the Faculty, they are not necessarily labeled as such. In fact, based on their characteristics and research focus, they could be considered Pi-type courses. However, the presence of professors who have developed training processes around the teaching of ethics allows ethical reflections to be more articulated with the contents and learning objectives of the sessions within the implementation of the courses.

Within the Faculty of Engineering, the Vice-Chancellor of Research and Creation established the Faculty's Ethics Committee (Universidad de Los Andes 3, n.d.). This made explicit the requirement to analyze the ethical implications of the research carried out by faculty members. For this, the committee has developed some tools that guide the review process and provide a step-by-step approach, starting with a self-classification of risk exercise for the research.

Within the follow-up on Ethics across the curriculum in the Faculty, the CEA has been articulated with the Engineering Education Support Unit. In addition to strengthening and expanding the offer of training processes in teaching ethics, it has been possible to accompany the development of the courses more effectively. At this moment, the Faculty has five CBU Epsilon-type courses.

As part of the Faculty of Engineering's Exemplary Teaching Plan and within the faculty's training process offer, the Teaching Support Unit has designed a series of strategies to favor the training processes of faculty professors at all levels. This includes Teaching Assistants for Master's and Doctoral degrees, Chair professors, and Plant professors.

For the Graduate Teaching Assistants of the Master's degree, those Master's students who accompany undergraduate engineering courses and develop teaching tasks, a cycle of training workshops in pedagogical tools was proposed. Within this cycle, one workshop addresses ethical reflections on engineering and the teaching role. An average of 80 students take these workshops each semester.

The Pedagogical Practices Seminar course is offered annually to doctoral students in charge of courses. This 16-week course seeks to foster spaces for discussion and reflection on the pedagogical exercise. Ethical implications are evidenced throughout the course from teaching work and engineering interventions. In addition, one of the sessions is led by the CEA, focusing specifically on the theoretical and practical recognition of ethical analyses in engineering. On average, 12 doctoral students attend this course annually.

4 Challenges of the Ethics Across the Curriculum of the Faculty of Engineering

Ethical training in engineering represents a significant challenge in itself as, among other things, it implies thinking of engineering as a task whose social impacts must be analyzed and considered in decision-making. This document presents the evolution of ethical interpretation in engineering, starting from loyalty to the client

and commercial subordination, passing through the optimization objective to arrive at a direct relationship with social well-being.

For the Faculty of Engineering at Los Andes University, this is a significant challenge and an urgent task to face, given the ABET accreditation of its programs and the commitment to disciplinary innovation and engineering education that it represents. This Faculty perspective has involved, and will involve, great efforts throughout the maturation of the proposals and will require spaces for deep reflection and collective construction of the Faculty from the entire university community. In this sense, the contribution of the Center for Applied Ethics has allowed the establishment of dialogue scenarios among the teachers who have been contributing to this discussion and a collective action driven from the departments as autonomous spaces but always linked with the idea of jointly configuring a robust Faculty with programs that aim through explicit objectives, teaching-learning activities, and evaluation, at the disciplinary development accompanied by the development of transversal competencies.

Creating educational materials that meet the needs of the courses has revolved around recognizing local contexts and current news. In this way, the development of the courses has been situated in an ethics teaching from the context. Within the need to dialogue different criteria and interpretations of reality and thus be able to nourish ethical deliberation, the CBU courses have enriched the relationships of students from different faculties. These strategies have led the University to assume ethical competence beyond a mission statement and as a daily practice.

The autonomy of the departments that are part of the Faculty of Engineering represents a considerable challenge concerning the number of courses and how the ethical component is made explicit or outside the course objectives. The risk with this approach to proposals through the curriculum is that it is interpreted as problematic that students may be receiving different training within the same institution. Their solution perspective is to teach a homogeneous course to address specific themes and competencies. This, as evidenced in this document, does not respond to the current needs of the training required by a student in the face of ethical competence.

Continuing to strengthen the training processes and discussion scenarios among the academic community is one strategy that allows us to continue consolidating good practices and assuming the shared responsibility of ethical training in engineering. Just as we seek to permeate the student from the transversality of ethical competence, constant reflection and teacher training (within the workshops for Master's Assistants, the course for Doctoral Assistants, and Epsilon-type teacher training) becomes a priority to appropriate the ethical approach contextualized through the curriculum.

Precisely within the strengthening of training scenarios in the inclusion of ethics, it is crucial to mention at this point that, recently, the CEA has partnered with Globethics to offer the course "How to Include Ethics in University Education" (Globethics, 2024). This course addresses the objectives of ethical training, valuable tools for ethical awareness, and tools for ethical deliberation. In this way, the proposal for the mainstreaming of ethics suggested by the University of Los Andes seeks to contribute to professors and, in general, other institutions and universities to integrate the teaching of ethics throughout the curriculum.

On the other hand, evaluating this competence and monitoring its development becomes a complex task. Accustomed to evaluating performance through pre-elaborated cases and focused on theoretical aspects, engineering professors must change the paradigm to propose real scenarios in which the circumstances raised require an ethical act. One of the objectives of the Faculty is for its graduates to be recognized for their integrity, placing ethical discernment in an increasingly important place. For this reason, it is desirable to take on the challenge of proposing authentic and comprehensive evaluation mechanisms that provide us with precise and

relevant information about the learning processes of the students and understand what has been achieved to think about how to improve the proposal of each of the programs of the Faculty.

Acknowledgments

We want to give special thanks to Gonzalo Cocomá, Linda A. Zuluaga, and Didier A. Santiago from the CEA, thank you for your support in writing this document and for providing us with access to the information they collected about the Faculty of Engineering.

5 References

- ABET. (2023). About ABET. <https://www.abet.org/>
- Beever, J., & Brightman, A. O. (2016). Reflexive principlism as an effective approach for developing ethical reasoning in engineering. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 22(1), 275–291.
- Bucciarelli, L. L. (2008). Ethics and engineering education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 141-149. doi:10.1080/03043790801979856
- Consejo Profesional Nacional de Ingeniería. (2003). Código de ética para el ejercicio de la Ingeniería en general y sus profesiones afines y auxiliares. Bogotá. https://www.copnia.gov.co/sites/default/files/node/page/field_insert_file/codigo_etica.pdf.
- Chance, S., Lawlor, R., Direito, I., & Mitchell, J. (2021). Above and beyond: ethics and responsibility in civil engineering. *Australasian Journal of Engineering Education*, 93-116. doi:10.1080/22054952.2021.1942767
- Duque M. y Reyes A., (2020) Una reforma relevante para los ingenieros del Siglo XXI: Lineamientos para una reforma curricular. En Langebaek Rueda, C.H., Hoyos Restrepo, J. M., & Zarur Latorre, F. S., (Ed.). *Reflexión curricular en la Universidad de los Andes*. Ediciones Uniandes-Universidad de los Andes.
- Figueiredo, J. (2021). A review and survey of Problem-Based Learning application in Engineering Education. *Academia Letters*, Article 412. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL412>
- Globethics. (2024). Cómo incluir la ética en la formación universitaria. Retrieved June 2, 2024, from <https://globethics.net/courses/como-incluir-la-etica-en-la-formacion-universitaria>
- Gwynne-Evans, A. J., Chetty, M., & Junaid, S. (2021). Repositioning ethics at the heart of engineering graduate attributes. *Australasian Journal of Engineering Education*, pp. 7–24. doi:10.1080/22054952.2021.1913882
- Langebaek Rueda, C.H., Hoyos Restrepo, J. M., & Zarur Latorre, F. S.,(2020). *Reflexión curricular en la Universidad de los Andes*. Ediciones Uniandes-Universidad de los Andes.
- Lattuca, Terenzini, and Volkwein, (2006). *Engineering Change: a Study of the impact of EC2000*. Executive Summary, 1-20. Recuperado el 26 de abril de 2023, <https://www.abet.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/EngineeringChange-executive-summary.pdf>
- Lee, E. A., Gans, N. R., Grohman, M. G., & Brown, M. J. (2019). Ethics as a rare bird: a challenge for situated studies of ethics in the engineering lab. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 284-304. doi:10.1080/23299460.2019.1605823
- Mitcham, C. (2009). A historico-ethical perspective on engineering education: from use and convenience to policy engagement. *Engineering Studies*, pp. 35–53. doi:10.1080/19378620902725166
- Montoya J. y Santiago D., (2020) Ética transversal: Un modelo de formación ética en la Universidad. En Langebaek Rueda, C.H., Hoyos Restrepo, J. M., & Zarur Latorre, F. S., (Ed.). *Reflexión curricular en la Universidad de los Andes*. Ediciones Uniandes-Universidad de los Andes.
- Universidad de los Andes. (s.f.). Universidad de los Andes - Colombia - Sitio oficial. Retrieved Abril 24, 2023, from <https://ingenieria.uniandes.edu.co/es/facultad/informacion-general/historia>
- Universidad de los Andes 2. (s.f.). Universidad de los Andes - Colombia - Sitio oficial. Retrieved Abril 24, 2023, from <https://investigacioncreacion.uniandes.edu.co/es/Cursos-Pi>
- Universidad de los Andes 3. (s.f.). Universidad de los Andes - Colombia - Sitio oficial. Retrieved Abril 24, 2023, from <https://ingenieria.uniandes.edu.co/es/investigacion-innovacion/investigacion/comites/comite-etica>